

Title: An extension to the Alpha Factor method for enhanced common cause failure analysis

Author: Mina Torabi, Marko Čepin

Description: The dataset associated with this publication contains the codes and the numerical data related to the analysis of system safety using the developed method.

File Formats: Codes are written in python language. The results, in the form of data plots, are in .csv format.

Size: Few MB

License: CC BY 4.0

Main publication doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2025.111964>

Access Instructions: The full dataset is available upon request. Contact Mina Torabi (mina.torabi@ncbj.gov.pl).

Funding information: This research was funded by the National Science Centre (NCN) in Poland through the Grant No. DEC-2024/08/X/ST8/00283.